

LEAD MICROPARTICLES IN GAME MEAT PRODUCTS – POTENTIAL RISKS FOR INGESTED EXPOSURE

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ABSTRACT

The present research describes a study of homemade meat products of wild boar shot with lead ammunition. Initially, X-ray radiography of the entire batch of sausages was performed to ascertain the presence of larger lead fragments. Afterward, visibly uncontaminated parts of sausages were examined using 3D scanning microtomography and the presence of lead microscopic particles was found. The results of quantitative analysis reported a high mean lead concentration than the maximum permitted levels according to EU Regulation 1881/2006.

Key words: lead ammunition, meat products, radiography, 3D scanning microtomography, quantitative analyzes.

Introduction

Lead is one of the most studied toxicants and a lot of scientific evidence demonstrates that lead is toxic to several physiological systems in vertebrates, including the nervous, renal, cardiovascular, reproductive, immune, and hematologic systems (Needleman *et al.*, 2002; Brown *et al.*, 2006; Verbrugge *et al.*, 2009). Once lead ammunition is fired and subsequent contact by the target tissues occurs fragmentation of lead ammunition to multiple macro and microparticles. These fragments in the game meat lead to risks of lead exposure associated with carnivores and human consumption.

Except for humans, the final consumers of shot game meat can be different animal species in which diets are meat or meat products shot with lead ammunition. Examples are hunting dogs and birds, predators and scavengers in zoos and in wildlife reserves, and other protected and endangered birds and mammals. According to Høgåsen *et al.*, 2016, feeding dogs of lead-shot game meat may represent a risk of lead intoxication. Cases of oral lead exposure falcons, alligators, cheetahs, etc. have been described (Camus *et al.*, 1998; Lance *et al.*, 2006; Rogers *et al.*, 2011; North *et al.*, 2015). The use of lead shots and bullets has been regulated in many countries around the world.

Materials and methods

Ten samples of raw-dried sausages of wild boar for direct consumption were tested. Raw dried sausages ($n = 10$) of the wild boar shot of lead ammunition are placed in a plastic bag and safety in fridge conditions at -20°C .

Initially, X-ray radiography of the entire batch of sausages was performed to ascertain the presence of larger lead fragments. Afterward, visibly uncontaminated parts of sausages were examined using 3D scanning microtomography and the presence of lead microscopic particles was found¹. The study was done with X-ray computerized microtomograph *Brucker SkyScan 1272* under the following conditions: voltage of the X-ray tube 60 kV Current 166 μA , filter Al 0.25 mm and

¹ The 3D microtomography and processing were performed by Prof. Dr. Dragomir Tochev in the Laboratory of computed tomography of Institute of Physical Chemistry " Rostislav Kaishev".

the amount of 3D pixels – 10 μm . Scanning consisted of three parts with a total length of 2 cm and a duration of 22 minutes each or a total of 67 minutes. The sample was placed in a plastic cylinder having an internal diameter equal to 1 cm. Thus, the total scanned volume was 6.28 cm^3 .

The samples were analyzed by the methods of electrothermal atomic absorption spectrophotometry using apparatus "Spectr AA 800" and "SpectrAA 220Z". The influence of chemical or spectral interference on lead measurement is minimized using a 1% ortho- H_3PO_4 solution modifier. The apparatus is calibrated for 0.0; 10.0; 25.0 and 50.0 ppb for the lead, with a spectral slot width of 0.5 nm and a wavelength of 283.3 nm.

The analysis and statistical processing of the data were performed by the computer program SPSS 19.0. The data are expressed as mean plus standard error. In this study, the assessment is made with a guaranteed probability of 0.95 (significance level $\alpha = 0,05$), where $p < 0,05$ was adopted as the lowest level of statistical reliability.

Results

The results of X-ray radiography of the whole batch of sausages visualize positively contrasting objects found in-depth (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: X-ray radiography of raw-dried sausages from wild boar shot with lead ammunition. Positively contrast objects (in circles) are present in the sausages.

Several "phases" of different ability to absorb X-rays were observed on the next few figures obtained after micro-computed tomography scanning: Black – air, cavities; darkest gray – slightly absorbing part of sausage, probably lard; lighter gray – meat/muscle tissue; a lot of bright, almost white objects – bones, cartilage, and/or other artifacts which are observed as a star-shaped object. A plastic tube in which is placed the sample is shown as a circle with a dark gray color (Fig. 2a and b).

After microstructure examination of a 3 mm segment from a randomly fixed part on sausage of wild boar meat, the positive contrast star-shaped object was observed (Fig. 2a). The size of this object with its rays is 0.1 mm. Calculate the absorption rate at 40 kV of Fe, Cu, Pb, and Au with

25%, 35%, 81%, and 92% respectively were obtained. Lead concentrations in this section showed elevated 3.11 mg/kg w.w.

Figure 2a: Computed microtomography in raw-dried sausage section from wild boar shot with lead ammunition. There is a lead particle of a star-shaped artifact formed in the right half of the figure (arrow). This lead particle has a diameter of 0.1 mm.

Figure 2b: Location of the lead (arrow) particle in the total scanned sample volume.

During the scanning of another section of the sausages was visible larger positive contrast object with star-shaped form (fig. 3 a, b). Its size is 0.3 mm and its absorption at 40 kV would be as follows: Fe – 57%, Cu – 73%, Pb – 99% and Au – 100%. The quantitative analysis in this section showed elevated lead concentrations of 5.64 mg/kg w.w. The others positively contrast objects in this sample with no star-shaped form, especially larger than 0.1 mm, are probably from connective tissue or adipose tissue (Fig. 3a, b).

Figure 3a: Computed microtomography in a raw-dried sausage section from wild boar shot with lead ammunition. In the lower right half of the figure, there is a contrast positive star-shaped artifact (arrow). The particle has a diameter of 0.3 mm and according to the degree of absorption, it has been defined as a lead.

Figure 3b: Location of the lead particle (arrow) in the total scanned sample volume.

The quantitative analysis showed a mean lead concentration of 0.919 ± 0.1104 mg/kg in all samples of raw-dried sausages prepared for consumption.

Discussion

The X-ray radiography systems produce two-dimensional (2D) shadow images of complete internal three-dimensional (3D) structures. Although the mechanical grinding of the meat, the two-dimensional radiographic images of raw-dried sausages from wild boar showed the presence of visible positively contrasting objects. According to Frank (1986), the two-dimensional radiographic technique is difficult to determine whether the observed objects are certainly metal particles.

The 3D computed tomography scanning according to Cornatzer et al. (2009) provides more accurate information on the structural determination of denser elements compared to 2D radiographic images. Computed X-ray microtomography allowed the internal structure of samples to be reconstructed and analyzed completely without destruction (SkyScan User Guide 1272, 2013). Through the use of high resolution computed microtomography lead microparticles have been successfully distinguished from other dense, mineral, or connective tissue elements.

The presence of elevated levels of lead in samples was also confirmed by the results obtained from the quantitative analysis. The average level of lead (0.919 ± 0.110 mg/kg w.w.) was higher than the maximum permitted levels (0.1 mg/kg w.w) according to EU Regulation 1881/2006.

The results of our qualitative and quantitative analyzes for lead content in the game meat and products were in line with the many global conclusions for the risk of accumulation of lead residues in the food chain (Tsuji et al., 1999; Mateo et al., 2006; Dobrowolska and Melosik, 2008; Hunt et al., 2009).

Conclusion

It could be concluded that the contact of shot lead ammunition with the target tissue causes a significant dispersion of lead microparticles, leading to contamination of predominantly leaded game meat products are an increased risk for the final consumer.

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References

1. Brown, C. S., J. Luebbert, D. Mulcahy, J. Schamber, D. H. Rosenberg. (2006). *Blood lead levels of wild Steller's eiders (Polysticta stelleri) and black scoters (Melanitta nigra) in Alaska using a portable blood lead analyzer*. Journal of Zoo and Wildlife Medicine, 37, 3, 361–363.
2. Camus, A.C., M. M. Mitchell, J. F. Williams, P. L. H. Jowett. (1998). *Elevated lead levels in farmed American alligators (Alligator mississippiensis) consuming nutria (Myocastor coypus) meat contaminated by lead bullets*. Journal of the World Aquaculture Society, 3, 370–376.
3. Cornatzer, W. E., E. F. Fogarty, E. W. Cornatzer. (2009). *Qualitative and quantitative detection of lead bullet fragments in random venison packages donated to the Community Action Food Centers of North Dakota, 2007*. In: R. T. Watson, M. Fuller, M. Pokras, W. G. Hunt (Eds.). *Ingestion of Lead from Spent Ammunition: Implications for Wildlife and Humans*. The Peregrine Fund, Boise, Idaho, USA, doi:10.4080/ilsa.2009.0111
4. Dobrowolska A., M. Melosik. (2008). *Bullet-derived lead in tissues of the wild boar (Sus scrofa) and red deer (Cervus elaphus)*. European Journal of Wildlife Research, 54, 2, 231–235, doi:10.1007/s10344-007-0134-y.
5. European Commission. *Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 of 19 December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs*. Official Journal of the European Union 20.12.2006 L364/5-L364/24; 2006.

6. Frank, A. (1986). *Lead fragments in tissues from wild birds: a cause of misleading analytical results*. *Science of Total Environment*; 54, 275–281.
7. Høgåsen, H. R., R. Ørnstrud, H. K. Knutsen, A. Bernhoft. (2016). *Lead intoxication in dogs: risk assessment of feeding dogs trimmings of lead-shot game*. *BMC Veterinary Research*, 12, 152, doi:10.1186/s12917-016-0771-z
8. Hunt, W. G., R. T. Watson, J. L. Oaks, C. N. Parish, K. K. Burnham, R. L. Tucker, J. R. Belthoff, and G. Hart. (2009). *Lead bullet fragments in venison from rifle-killed deer: potential for human dietary exposure*. Reproduced in R. T. Watson, M. Fuller, M. Pokras, and W. G. Hunt (Eds.). *Ingestion of Lead from Spent Ammunition: Implications for Wildlife and Humans*. The Peregrine Fund, Boise, Idaho, USA. doi: 10.4080/ilsa.2009.0112
9. Lance, V. A., T. R. Horn, R. M. Elsey, A. de Peyster. (2006). *Chronic incidental lead ingestion in a group of captive-reared alligators (Alligator mississippiensis), possible contribution to reproductive failure*. *Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 142, 30–35.
10. Mateo, R., M. Rodríguez-de la Cruz, M. Reglero, P. Camarero. (2006). *Transfer of lead from shot pellets to game meat during cooking*. *Science of the Total Environment*, 372, 2–3, 480–485.
11. Needleman, H. L., C. McFarland, R. B. Ness, S. E. Fienberg, M. J. Tobin. (2002). *Bone Lead Levels in Adjudicated Delinquents, A Case Control Study*, *Neurotoxicology and Teratology*, 24, 711–717.
12. North, M. A., E. P. Lane, K. Marnewick, P. Caldwell, G. Carlisle, L. C. Hoffman. (2015). *Suspected lead poisoning in two captive cheetahs (Acinonyx jubatus jubatus) in South Africa, in 2008 and 2013*. *Journal of the South African Veterinary Association*, 86, 1, 1286, pp 1–5. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/jsava.v86i1.1286>.
13. Rogers T. A., B. Bedrosian, J. Graham, K. R. Foresman. (2010). *Lead Exposure in Large Carnivores in the Greater Yellowstone Ecosystem*. *The Journal of Wildlife Management*, 1–8; doi: 10.1002/jwmg. 277.
14. SkyScan 1272 *User manual*. Bruker micro CT, 2013, 4–11.
15. Tsuji, L. J. S., E. Nieboer, J. D. Karagatzides, R. M. Hanning, B. Katapatuk. (1999). *Lead Shot Contamination in Edible Portions of Game Birds and Its Dietary Implications*. *Ecosystem Health*, 5, 3, 183–192.
16. Verbrugge, L. A., S. G. Wenzel, J. E. Berner, A. C. Matz. (2009). *Human exposure to lead from ammunition in the circumpolar north*. In: R. T. Watson, M. Fuller, M. Pokras, W. G. Hunt (Eds.). *Ingestion of Lead from Spent Ammunition: Implications for Wildlife and Humans*. The Peregrine Fund, Boise, Idaho, USA. DOI 10.4080/ilsa.2009.0110.